

Risk Assessment of Project Based Learning Failure via Bayesian Belief Networks and Analytical Hierarchy Process – A Literature Review

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Abstract

Project-based learning has been used in engineering education because of its expected effectiveness in developing students' professional knowledge. With a growing number of Project-based learning research and practices in engineering education, a systematic review was conducted regarding the use of Project based learning and risks of failure. It has been noticed that risks in the implementation using Bayesian Belief Networks and Analytical Hierarchy Process have not been addressed in the current reviewed literature, and even less attention has been paid to risk responses. The aim of the study is the identification of the risks on the use of the Project-Based Learning Method on the teaching of Operations Management disciplines to engineers and propose a method to combine the risks by using Bayesian Belief Networks and Analytical Hierarchy Process to establish prioritization for responses. The author conducted an in-depth literature review of Journals indexed in Scientific Databases, such as Google Scholar, Scielo, Scopus, Web of Knowledge, and Journals related to engineering education listed in JCR Journal Citation Reports. Based on the information obtained from the researched literature, respective actions are recommended to improve the method currently used to attain operational excellence in the teaching of Operational Management. Recommendations on future research directions for engineering education researchers are proposed to optimize Project-based learning curriculum design.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; PBL; Risk Assessment, BBN, AHP

1 Introduction

Student-centered teaching methods by using Project-based learning (PBL) have been widely used. Still, universities find it difficult to deal with unexpected issues that arise during the implementation phase and often return to traditional teaching methods (Henderson, 2012). Therefore, it is important to identify, describe and deal with risk factors that have a direct impact on PBL's.

In this study, the author conducted a literature review to identify and list key risk factors when implementing PBL in engineering education. Being aware of these risks and how to respond to them can improve the chances of success when implementing PBL to enhance student learning and provide a sustainable teaching method at universities. It has been noticed that current literature on the use of PBL in engineering education has not addressed the risks of PBL failure, and even less attention has been paid to risk responses to ensure excellence in projects.

The objective is to propose a method for risk assessment via Bayesian Belief Networks (BBN) and Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), to identify the risks and responses to ensure successful PBL's are conducted in collaboration with local companies. If the operational structure is not defined, risks are not identified, and the proper responses are not provided, PBL can fail. T

his study assesses the risks and completes a gap in the literature by assessing the risk factors on the use of the Project-Based Learning Method on the teaching of Operations Management to engineers. The diversity of risk factors presented here highlight the complexity of implementing PBL in engineering education. To be addressed, most of these risks require proper responses, and this need justifies this project. If risks are not identified and appropriately addressed, PBL projects can fail, and the students, professors, and partner organizations will not obtain the expected benefits.

This paper is significant since it will help the development of skills and practice of professors, students and increase the quality of PBL as well as universities sustainability. It is noteworthy here that the study focus is on Project Based Learning that involves companies. Successful PBL's in this case will result in a significant reduction of business risks and achievement of excellence in quality and organizational safety by supporting local companies to attain the following goals: 1 - Seeking creative, strategic directions to monitor the changes in the economy, market, and technologies to achieve operational excellence; 2 - Studying modern trends in the use of risk analysis tools aimed at improving product quality and safety; 3 - Studying modern and automated (digital) processes for optimization of organizational strategies to improve results and reduce costs; 4 - Seeking technologies to ensure maximum efficiency and meeting specific market needs; 5 - Seeking ways to add value to products and services through continuous improvement of products and services to retain customers and sustainability wingers.

None of the studies present herein dealt with risk assessment and its impacts on PBL. The literature research revealed that most previous studies addressed PBL and challenges without giving a methodology for risk prioritization using Bayesian Belief Networks and AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process in PBL. The paper provides responses to the following research questions: 1 – What are the most significant risk factors for using PBL in engineering courses? 2 – What are the risks when trying the application of the method to support the operations management of companies? 3 – How to combine the risks by using BBN and AHP to establish prioritization for responses? In sections 3, 4, and 5, several papers are cited, and none of the studies present herein dealt with risk assessment of PBL using BBN and AHP. This paper is divided into five sections; the first introduces the concepts of the study, the second describes PBL, Section 3 the challenges and Risk Assessment of PBL Failure. Section 4 presents BBN (Bayesian Belief Network), section 5 deals with AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process), Section 6 describes Methodology, section 7 results, and section 8 conclusion.

2 Project-Based Learning

Previous significant studies about PBL Methodology and Challenges in its implementation are presented in subsections 2.1 and 2.2.

2.1 Design of PBL Method

Previous significant studies about PBL are presented herein. Moliner et al. (2019) developed a work focused on the description of the experience of using PBL methodology in Materials Science courses, conducted by four different Spanish universities on different engineering degrees. The author analysed and evaluated how the PBL was perceived by the students and the lecturers that took part in the PBL process. Setiawan (2019) conducted a study focusing on the implementation of PBL, specifically on the opportunities and challenges. The students choose their own topic, identify, and explain what the topic is, why they choose that, and how they solve the problem. Thevathayan (2018) presented an experience evolving a hybrid-teaching model by using the action research cycle plan-act-observe-reflect over 3 semesters. The main novelty of the approach was the use of projects with varying levels, which gave students an enjoyable and beneficial project experience. Marques (2018) proposed a formative monitoring method to help students be aware of their individual and team performance. The results obtained indicated that PBL was effective in enhancing the learning experience in the instructional scenario studied. Schneider (2020) used PBL as a means of enhancing student engagement. The activities of the partnership focused on the co-design and enactment of and co-reflection on PBL units. Daun (2016) discussed results from the long-term application of such a course design in a graduate setting. In addition, he indicated that project-based learning techniques foster different teaching goals in graduate and undergraduate settings. Du et al. (2013) developed a framework of change in educational culture for sustainability by using a PBL methodology. This framework aims to inspire curriculum design for sustainability education and analyse the implementation of PBL in each cultural context. Palmer and W. Hall (2011) presented the result of PBL offering in engineering PBL at Griffith University in Australia. The author observed that students generally enjoyed the experience. The aspects needing improvement were listed and documented. García-Martín and E.Pérez (2017) presented a method to guide teachers in using PBL principles and several instructional design models. In particular, the process deals with the definition of a problem facing three fundamental issues in active learning, especially in PBL: Students' Motivation, Supporting Students' Work, and

Autonomous Working. The authors focused on academic contexts where instructors are starting to use this methodology and students are not used to dealing with ill-structured projects. Du Bani et al. (2018) presented the main challenges facing PBL. The challenges included the type of projects, how to team up students, how to proceed with planning, how to swap planning outputs among teams, and how to implement a Project.

2.2 Challenges and Risk Assessment of PBL Failure

Previous significant studies about the Challenges of PBL are presented herein. The survey of Henderson et al. (2012) mentioned that faculty are aware of student-centered teaching methods but find it challenging to deal with unexpected issues that arise during the implementation phase and thus often return to traditional teaching methods. Kjellberg et al. (2015) stated that implementing PBL is the holistic perspective of the project and that in most projects, the non-technical responsibilities are not clearly defined. According to the author, the complete infrastructure is not defined, probably due to the lack of a holistic project perspective and project management methods. These authors also stated that novice teams affected knowledge transfer and communication within extended teams, affecting group dynamics, commitment, and responsibilities. The authors highlighted that lack of teacher teams leads to one teacher acting as both examiner and PM. The authors also emphasized that the "two-hats" issue added to the teacher workload and created emotional stress due to the lack of tools and support and the constant brooding on addressing issues that appear. Beddoes et al. (2010) explained that challenges about implementation and execution of PBL are both theoretical and practical. Theoretically, debates remain over the best approach to incorporate PBL and the extent of performance necessary to benefit students. Some engineering educators argue that the maximum benefits of PBL will not be obtained unless it is implemented across the entire curriculum and all at once (Inelmen, 2003).

On the other hand, some argue that due to the significant differences between PBL and traditional methods, instructors should start with small-scale initiatives so they can incrementally familiarize themselves with PBL (Hansen, Cavers, & George, 2003). The changing roles of the teacher and the student are widely recognized as two of the largest barriers to the implementation of PBL (Prince & Felder, 2006; Strobel, 2009). PBL can be difficult for faculty and students "because it challenges them to see learning and knowledge in new ways" and blurs boundaries (Savin-Baden, 2007, p. 24). For instance, students may be hostile to PBL because they are unaccustomed to the level of personal responsibility required and may experience conflicts with team members (Prince & Felder, 2006). And teachers, too, often find it difficult to adjust to PBL (Prince & Felder, 2006; Thomas, 2000). Furthermore, institutional difficulties include resources, program sustainability, scalability, physical facilities, and management (Bielefeldt et al., 2009)

3 BBN (Bayesian Belief Network)

BBN has been widely used in the industry to estimate risks. Bayesian-based reliability was used to estimate the corrosion (Yang et al., 2016). Bayesian network (BN) was used to ease knowledge acquisition of causal dependence in CREAM (Ashrafi et al., 2016). The Bayesian variable was used in the selection to analyze regular resolution IV two-level fractional factorial designs (Chipman et al., 2016). BNs, also known as BBN's, are a causal structure used by probability risk analysis specialists to obtain information about basic risk events and the necessary interventions to address risks (Rechenthin, 2004; Mosleh, 1992). The use of BNs in fields related to safety, maintenance, and reliability has been increasing quickly (Mahadevan, 2001). Bayesian methods have been used comprehensively in many applications and provide a structure for addressing the limitations of human reliability analysis (Podofillini and Dang, 2013; Mosleh and Apostolakis, 1986; Droguett et al., 2004; Groth and Swiler, 2013). None of the above previous studies deals with the application of BBN to the manufacturing or servicing of rotors. The objective of BN methodology is to allow more straightforward predictions of risk events; it is a structure representing arguments when uncertainty exists. The nodes represent the variables, and the arcs the direct dependency between those.

4 AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process)

Saaty (1980) was the first to use AHP as a decision-making tool to provide the relative weight of criteria based on a hierarchy structure. The author proposed the use of pairwise comparison to evaluate alternatives. The

method has been used extensively to solve complex decision problems. It divides a difficult issue into smaller parts aiming at ranking them hierarchically. Thus, the relative importance of alternatives is weighed accordingly. In this paper, AHP is utilized to consider/prioritize the key risks affecting the stacking process. The AHP is an excellent tool to provide weight for the different risk levels; the first phase is to create a pairwise evaluation matrix (A), as introduced by (Saaty 1980), by utilizing the relative importance scale. The matrix A represents a pairwise evaluation matrix where each element "a_{ij}"(i, j = 1, 2, ..., n) represents the proportional importance of two compared elements (i and j). The higher the value, the stronger the first element preference(i) over the second (j). (MIs and Otcenaskova, 2013).

5 Methodology

To achieve the proposed objective and respond to the research questions, an in-depth literature review of Journals indexed in Scientific Databases, such as Google Scholar, Scielo, Scopus, and Web of Knowledge, identified the risk factors on the use of PBL. The following Journals related to engineering education listed in JCR Journal Citation Reports Full Journal List were also reviewed for state-of-the-art papers on the subject: 1 – International journal of engineering education – Ireland; 2 - Journal of engineering education – USA; 3 - Journal of professional issues in engineering education and practice – USA; 4 - Computer applications in engineering education – USA; 5 - International journal of electrical engineering education – England; 6 - European journal of engineering education. For selecting the publications of interest, they were searched by title, abstract, keywords and the focus was on the papers published in the last five years. The following keywords were used: Active Learning; Engineering Education; PBL; Risk Assessment, BBN, AHP. The searched papers were reviewed by reading the abstract and introduction; those with relevance to the research objectives were selected. In this project, 50 research papers were selected among 120 to identify risk factors in the PBL use and implementation. The papers covering problem-based learning and not covering Design of PBL and challenges/risk assessment of PBL failure were disregarded. A list of risk factors found in the researched literature was then prepared. A quality management and planning tool named Relationship Digraph was used to cluster the risk factors into categories and establish the cause-and-effect relationship to the failure of PBL. For further study, it is recommended to create a survey in Google forms to obtain the probability for the risk factors from Students, Professors, and Organization Leaders. The probabilities for each risk factor obtained should be combined with BBN (Bayesian Belief Networks) to get the probabilities for the risk categories. AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process) should then be used to find the impact for the risk categories. The last step would be implementing risk responses to address the risk categories as required by their RPN (Risk Priority Number).

6 Results

The quality tools Process Map and Relationship Digraph were used to identify and classify the risk factors; a traditional PBL Process Map was prepared to determine the risks when trying to apply the PBL projects in universities to support the operations management of companies in the region. The flowchart of Figure 1. shows the structure generally practiced in the conduction of PBL projects and the risks presented in each step. The letters in red represent the learning principles (category) of risks: C: Cognitive Learning Failure, S: Social Learning Failure, and T: Theory and Practice Learning.

Figure 1. structure generally practiced in conduction of PBL projects and risks.

The risk factors impacting PBL failure were identified in the researched literature. The risk factors were clustered into categories to establish the cause-and-effect relationship to the failure of PBL. Affinity Diagram was used

to organize the risk factors within 3 learning principles and 9 categories, as suggested by Xiangyun (2013). Risk factors leading to each risk category were identified based on the researched literature, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Risk Factors impacting PBL failure.

Type	Categories	Risks Identification	Risk Factors
C: Cognitive Learning Failure	CA: No Standardization of PBL Procedure	C1	Lack of procedure for PBL process
		C2	Students and professors not appropriately trained on the PBL procedure
		C3	Lack of standard work for the execution of PBL's
	CB: PBL specific requirements not defined accurately	C4	Poor explanation of expectations to students
		C5	Lack of background definition on principle behind projects
		C6	No clear definition of requirements
	CC: Wrong Choice of Project	C7	Project complexity incompatible with time and resources
		C8	The project not related to discipline
		C9	Workload too heavy for the student
		C10	The low ability of students (slow learner)
S: Social Learning Failure	SA: Team Building practices not used	S1	Number of Students in project inadequate (too big or too small)
		S2	Project team members not equally strong
		S3	Assign students to teams rather than let them select the team themselves
	SB: PBL Professor not active in the project	S4	Professor does not give feedback on the project
		S5	Nonexistence of guidelines for team operation in the project
		S6	Students not encouraged by professors
	SC: Team lack of Motivation	S7	Some of the students not active in the project
		S8	No focus on the project
		S9	Relationship professor and student not good
		S10	Students and Professor lack patience and enthusiasm
T: Theory and Practice Learning Failure	TA: PBL Professor not prepared for the project	T1	Professor does not support knowledge base construction.
		T2	Professor does not support Argument base construction.
		T3	Lack of professor technical content knowledge and experience
		T4	Professor has no industrial skills.
	TB: No definition of PBL records organization	T5	Lack of definition for the project content organization
		T6	No definition of project report content
		T7	Problem-solving methods not defined
	TC: Students not prepared for the PBL	T8	Students are not familiar with the specific process theory behind PBL.
		T9	Students have no knowledge of Quality Tools for problem-solving
		T10	Students not trained on specific PBL industrial process

Based on Table 1, BBN was prepared, logical connective OR is utilised since risk factors are independent. The diagram in Figure 2 shows the BBN combining all risk factors in the different learning principles categories.

Figure 2. BBN combining all risk factors

When applying the model in future studies probabilities for each risk factor needs to be elicited from students and professors. The probability values are then loaded into a BBN software and by sensitive analysis the probabilities of each risk category can be obtained.

To obtain the impact for each risk category the AHP needs to be utilized. Pairwise comparative matrices should be prepared as shown in Table 2. An interview process needs to be conducted to obtain from professors and students the degree of impact of each risk on the failure of PBL. As an example, the following question need to be made: Considering that PBL fails, what is the importance of one category (example: CA), relative to the other (example: CB) in causing the failure? In this case suppose the score 7 is attributed based on Table 3, so $a_{12}=7$. This means that element CA has a very strong importance relative to element CB. For symmetry, it is assumed that if $a_{12} = 7$, then $a_{21} = 1/7$. The relative importance for all other risks is estimated in a similar way and translated into the numerical pairwise comparison matrix shown in Table 2. Based on the completed pairwise comparative matrix, the weight values (impact) of risks can be quantitatively calculated using the eigenvector corresponding to the maximum eigenvalue of pairwise comparative matrices as the weighted values. Table 5 is used to obtain the probability and Impact Score for all risk categories.

Table 2. Risk Factors impacting PBL failure.

	CA	CB	CC	SA	SB	SC	TA	TB	TC	Weight
CA	1	7								
CB	1/7	1								
CC			1							
SA				1						
SB					1					
SC						1				
TA							1			
TB								1		
TC									1	

Table 3. Risk Factors

impacting PBL failure

Saaty scale	Definition
1	Equal importance
3	Medium importance
5	High importance
7	Very high importance
9	Extreme importance

The global risk score and class need to be determined using the risk scoring matrix shown in Figure 3 (Hyun et al., 2015). As an example, the final risk score for the risk category CA is obtained in the following way: Considering the probability for CA is 0.6 and the impact 0.17, based on Table 4 the probability rating score is (value: 4) and the impact rating score is (value: 5) for the risk CA. To obtain the final risk score for CA Figure 3 is referenced, in this case the final score is (value: 20).

Table 4. Probability and Impact Score.

Probability Level Score			Impact Level Score		
Score	Probability Level	Probability	Score	Impact Level	Impact
5	Expected	More than 0,80	5	High	More than 0,16
4	Very probable	0,51-0,80	4	Elevated	0,12-0,16
3	Probable	0,31-0,50	3	Moderated	0,08-0,11
2	Improbable	0,11-0,30	2	Low	0,04-0,07
1	Almost no probability	Less than 0,10	1	Limited	Less than 0,04

The risk scoring matrix in Figure 3 combines the probability and impact score for each risk and provides the final risk score

		RISK					
		Limited	Low	Moderate	Elevated	High	
		1	2	3	4	5	
Probability	Almost no probability	1	1	2	3	4	5
	Unlikely	2	2	4	6	8	10
	Probable	3	3	6	9	12	15
	Very probable	4	4	8	12	16	20
	Expected	5	5	10	15	20	25
Risk Factor Classification							
1-5	Insignificant	6-9	Tolerable	10-16	Undesireble	17-25	Intolerable

Figure 3. risk scoring matrix

For further study, the quantitative values for probabilities and impact step could be obtained by administrating a Survey in Google Forms to students, professors, and Partner. As explained before, the next step is to consolidate all the probabilities obtained with the survey using BBN to obtain the probability of each category of risk. The risk categories can then be evaluated by a pairwise comparison to define the weights of each category. The Combination of Bayesian Belief Networks results with Analytical Hierarchy Process results will determine the final score for the risks and the required prioritization for risk responses.

7 Conclusion

As proposed in the introduction, the study demonstrated that AHP in conjunction with BBN can be used to assess and prioritize the risk factors of PBL failure in future studies. An in-depth analysis of current literature about the subject allowed the identification of risk factors in this process. The preparation of a global risk matrix is proposed since it provides key information considering identifying and prioritizing the potential risks that could cause PBL failure. It is an effective decision-making process for universities. This study shows evidence that PBL, in general, is subjected to a great variety of risks, some of them capable of compromising the sustainability of the universities. In this regard, probabilistic risk analysis plays a significant role in understanding and implementing risk responses to avoid failure. An in-depth search for previous work dealing with risks in PBL was conducted and is described herein and a model is proposed for risk assessment. This study is significant because understanding the significant risks in the PBLs process can influence the decision of professors and university engineering school coordinators. The application of this innovative risk assessment method in the PBL process fills a gap in the literature since no previous work dealt with this specific subject.

As expected, the contribution is significant since risk assessment in the PBL process permits decision-makers to assign funds for critical activities that can impact universities' sustainability. As initially proposed, a model for risk assessment of PBL failure is being proposed that allows the combined application of AHP and Bayesian Networks to prioritize risks. The proposed application sought to analyze and define the primary risk factors and critical events that could lead to a failure in PBL. In response to the first question, "1 - What are the most

significant risk factors on the use of PBL at engineering courses?" a table with the risk and risk categories is presented. In response to the second question, *"2 – What are the risks when trying the application of the method to support the operations managements of companies?"* a table with the risk and risk categories is presented. In response to the third question, *"3 – How the risks could be combined by using BBN and AHP to establish prioritization for responses?"* a method is proposed that allows the combination of risk factors by using BBN and AHP and this demonstration should be done in future studies. It is believed that the present study will augment the knowledge of professors, engineering students, and engineering school coordinators and help in the application process.

8 References

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